

Large displacement analysis of masonry structures coupling enhanced virtual elements and damage-friction interfaces

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Enhanced virtual elements are coupled with damaging-frictional interfaces.
- Corotational approach is used to account for geometric nonlinearity.
- Procedure is proposed to compute nodal forces due to body loads in virtual elements.
- Large displacement analysis of masonry block structures is performed.
- Numerical outcomes are compared with experimental and analytical solutions.

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ABSTRACT

Enhanced virtual elements are coupled with cohesive interfaces to create a numerical tool tailored for large displacement analysis of block structures. The model is particularly suitable for masonry composed of stones or bricks connected with or without mortar. Each masonry block is modeled with a single elastic virtual element (VE), based on a divergence-free polynomial approximation of the stress field within the element, and the corotational formulation recently developed by the authors. These stabilization-free VEs are coupled, for the first time, with damaging-frictional interfaces representing the layers interconnecting the blocks, which are innovatively extended to the large displacement framework. Furthermore, in the context of virtual elements, a novel method is presented to accurately evaluate nodal forces equivalent to body loads when internal degrees of freedom are not available.

Some numerical applications are performed to investigate the capability of the proposed formulation to reproduce the response of single masonry elements and more complex structural schemes. The analyses prove that the model reproduces well the main nonlinear mechanisms due to the presence of large displacements and material degradation caused by cracking and friction. Finally, the model potential to handle irregular stone walls is proved through numerical–experimental comparison.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, many numerical models have been developed to simulate and predict the behavior of masonry structures, aiming to balance numerical efficiency and result accuracy. These models are traditionally classified based on the scale of analysis, thus distinguishing between macromechanical, micromechanical, and multiscale approaches [1–3].

The first group, i.e., the macromechanical models, treats masonry as a homogeneous continuum, where the individual constituents (bricks or blocks and mortar joints) are not distinguishable. These models adopt phenomenological constitutive laws to capture the key features of the nonlinear mechanical response of masonry material, considering both the simplified hypothesis of isotropic behavior and the more advanced assumption of anisotropic response in the elastic and inelastic ranges [4–6].

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The second group, i.e., the micromechanical models, separately describes each masonry component and, possibly, their interaction behavior. These can be further subdivided into detailed and simplified models, as proposed in [7]. The first describe blocks and mortar through continuum elements and the unit–mortar interfaces with discontinuous elements; the latter consider joints as mechanical units representing both mortar and unit–mortar interaction and adopt expanded units with nonlinear behavior or linear elastic response, sometimes with potential crack interfaces embedded. Simplified micromechanical models are also referred to as mesoscale models [8]. In this framework, the Finite Element Method is a well established modeling approach [8–10], but the Discrete Element Method (DEM) has also taken hold in the last decades. The DEM idealizes masonry material as an assembly of bodies, the masonry units, interacting at the boundaries through mortar joints regarded as contact surfaces between bodies. A variety of formulations has been proposed, whose main differences can be found in the contact assumptions, block representation, and solution methods [11].

To date, the micromechanical approach appears to be the most accurate modeling strategy available for simulating masonry behavior, but its applicability is limited to the analysis of small elements or structural details, due to the high computational costs and the effort required to generate the detailed numerical model.

Finally, the third group, i.e., the multiscale models, splits the structural problem into two scales: macro and micro. These models are typically used to analyze the behavior of masonry with regular texture, where a Representative Volume Element (RVE) of the periodic media can be identified. Hence, the material constitutive response of the homogeneous model used at the structural scale is derived from the detailed analysis of the RVE at the microscale. A weak or strong coupling between the two scales can be established depending on whether an a priori homogenization is performed or a step-by-step RVE-based homogenization procedure is developed [12–16].

Relying on the above considerations, this paper proposes a new simplified micromechanical model for masonry that speeds up the numerical simulations, while preserving the accuracy of the results. Particularly, the model merges the advantageous features of the interface elements and those of the modern Virtual Element Method (VEM).

Interface models, often incorporated into finite element codes, represent a consolidated tool to represent the interaction and link between different materials (or structures) and capture failure mechanisms due to the opening and sliding of the two surfaces in contact. Indeed, nonlinear material effects, due to damage, unilateral contact, and friction, have been included in many cohesive interface models [17]. Typically, the interface constitutive law is formulated in terms of tractions and displacement jumps expressed in the interface local reference system. This is defined as the tangential and normal directions at the interface plane in the initial undeformed configuration, thus referring to the small displacement and strain theory. However, several attempts have been made to include the nonlinear geometric effects [18–22], mainly based on the definition of a reference middle surface of the interface element in the current configuration for the calculation of the normal and tangential directions to the interface. This allows for the exploration of applications where significant changes in the deformed configuration occur, leading to combined instability effects and catastrophic fracture propagation.

On the other hand, the VEM is a modern numerical procedure [23] developed to overcome some limitations of the classical Finite Element Method. High flexibility in the number of nodes and shape of the elements are among the key benefits of this technique, while the need for stabilization terms to prevent zero-energy modes represents a major drawback of the originally proposed version of the method. Hence, many advanced formulations have been developed leading to stabilization-free elements [24–27]. Recently, the VEM has been introduced in the corotational formulation [28,29] to efficiently account for the nonlinear geometric effects due to large displacements and rotations in the small strain setting, thus avoiding the complexity of the finite strain theory.

Virtual elements (VEs), in their early version requiring stabilization, and interface elements have been coupled to track the fracture propagation process in polycrystalline random composites [30], to simulate the evolution of cohesive fracture in two-dimensional bodies [31] and, also, to analyze cracking of cement-based composites [32]. In this work, stabilization-free VEs are combined with interface elements to generate a powerful numerical tool capable of accounting for the material and geometric nonlinear effects characterizing masonry response to external loads. Particularly, each masonry block/brick is discretized with a single linear elastic virtual element based on an enhanced representation of the stress field within the element and on the corotational approach for describing the large-displacement induced nonlinearity [28]. In addition, mortar joints are modeled by interface finite elements, relying on a large displacement formulation. All the nonlinear effects due to damage, unilateral contact and friction, are considered to be concentrated at the interfaces, thus making the model capable of representing the fracture propagation phenomenon typically occurring at the unit–mortar contact surfaces. The VEM is chosen for the block representation, due to its versatility in modeling general polygonal elements and its high flexibility in terms of node number and position. This allows for refined interface discretization, although avoiding dense finite element meshes for the units, with a relevant computational cost saving.

The work offers some innovative contributions in terms of formulation, methodology, and application. In fact, the interface formulation previously adopted in [17,30,33], based on the small displacement hypothesis, is here extended to the large displacement theory. These interface elements are then coupled, for the first time, to the corotational stabilization-free VEs formulated in [28]. The resulting model is employed to explore response of masonry structures, exploiting a new and computationally efficient modeling strategy where each masonry unit is discretized with only one VE. Finally, a novel procedure to accurately evaluate the nodal forces equivalent to body loads in the virtual element context is presented.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 outlines the basics of the model, including the description of static and kinematic operators in the nonlinear framework. Sections 3 and 4 are dedicated to the enhanced corotational VEM formulation and the interface large displacement model adopted, respectively. Section 5 proves the model efficiency using some numerical applications and compares analytical and experimental outcomes with the numerical results obtained through the proposed approach. Section 6 concludes by remarking on the main contributions of the paper.

2. Problem formulation

In this section, the model formulation including both geometric and material nonlinear effects is described. Firstly, kinematic and static quantities are introduced and, then, information on the constitutive laws adopted is provided.

Let us consider two masonry blocks, occupying the domains Ω_0^j and Ω_0^i , separated by a cohesive interface, represented by the line Γ_0 in the two-dimensional (2D) framework, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The cohesive interface can either represent only the interaction between blocks in dry masonry, or also model the response of mortar layers in non-dry masonry.

Under a generic loading history, the two bodies undergo a motion ϕ that causes a change of their configuration and the separation of the initially overlapped upper, Γ_0^+ , and lower, Γ_0^- , sides of the interface moving to Γ^+ and Γ^- . Indeed, each material point belonging to $\Gamma_0^+ = \Gamma_0^- = \Gamma_0$ in the reference/initial configuration can split into two points, lying on Γ^+ and Γ^- , in the current configuration. This implies that the displacement fields u and v defined along the global X -axis and Y -axis, respectively, are discontinuous on Γ_0 . The displacement vector $\mathbf{u} = [uv]^T$ is defined as $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}^0$, being $\mathbf{X}^0 = [X^0 Y^0]^T$ and $\mathbf{X} = [X Y]^T$ the material point positions in the reference and current configuration, respectively, expressed in the global system (O, X, Y) .

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of two masonry blocks separated by a cohesive interface.

It is assumed that the deformation gradient, given by $\mathbf{F} = \partial \phi / \partial \mathbf{X}^0$ and subjected to the constraint $J = \det \mathbf{F} > 0$ to ensure that material area elements remain positive, is not continuous on the embedded surface Γ_0 . The first Piola–Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{P} is introduced as the corresponding stress measure.

The separation displacements are used as a measure of the interface deformation and result as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{X}^+ - \mathbf{X}^- = \mathbf{u}^+ - \mathbf{u}^- \quad (1)$$

being $\mathbf{X}^+ \in \Gamma^+$ and $\mathbf{X}^- \in \Gamma^-$ the current positions of points initially lying on Γ_0 , for which multiple mapping can exist. The static quantities, work-conjugated to displacement jumps $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$, are the cohesive forces transmitted through the interface, which are collected in the first Piola–Kirchhoff traction vector $\hat{\mathbf{t}}$.

Considering that the uniqueness of the interface location, Γ_0 , is lost during the deformation mapping, the middle line Γ_m in the interface current configuration is assumed to identify the tangential, x_T , and normal, x_N , directions at the interface (see Fig. 1) required to express the constitutive relationship.

The Virtual Work equivalence of the whole mechanical system can be expressed in the reference configuration as:

$$\sum_{k=i,j} \int_{\Omega_0^k} \delta \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{P} d\Omega_0^k + \int_{\Gamma_0} \delta \mathbf{s}^T \mathbf{t} d\Gamma_0 = \delta \mathcal{L}_{ext} \quad (2)$$

where δ denotes the virtual variation of the corresponding quantity, \mathcal{L}_{ext} is the virtual work of the external loads, and $\mathbf{s} = [s_T \ s_N]^T$ and $\mathbf{t} = [t_T \ t_N]^T$ are the displacement jump and traction vectors expressed in the interface local coordinate system (x_T, x_N) . Particularly, \mathbf{s} is obtained by pre-multiplying $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ by the interface rotation matrix \mathbf{R}^3 that relates the global (X, Y) and local (x_T, x_N) reference systems, i.e. $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{R}^3(\mathbf{u})\hat{\mathbf{s}}$.

Material nonlinearity is assumed to be concentrated at the interfaces. Hence, the elastic constitutive response is considered for the bricks/blocks composing the masonry, while a friction-damage law is assumed for the interfaces, as detailed in the following sections.

3. Virtual elements

The 2D domain Ω_0 occupied by the masonry blocks, given by $\Omega_0 = \Omega_0^j \cup \Omega_0^i$ for the example case in Fig. 1, is discretized into nonoverlapping polygonal virtual elements. Each polygon E is characterized by the area Ω_E and its boundary $\partial\Omega_E$ is composed by n_V vertices, n_E edges, and n nodes. In the spirit of the proposed modeling approach, each virtual element models the block surface and half-thickness of the mortar joints in case of non-dry masonry, and only the block surface in case of dry masonry.

The enhanced divergence-free virtual element method proposed in [24], and then extended by the authors to the corotational framework

Fig. 2. Kinematics of the virtual element: rigid and deformation parts.

[28], is adopted. The corotational formulation accounts for the nonlinear geometric effects due to large displacements but small strains in the element. The key idea is to decompose the kinematics of the element into its rigid and deformation parts, by introducing a local system moving with the element during its motion. Hence, the element response is computed based on the small deformation displacements computed in the corotational system, i.e., those exhibited by the element after the large rigid displacements have been exploited. Accordingly, the following sections, devoted to recalling the main governing equations of the adopted corotational enhanced virtual element method [28], foresee the use of the infinitesimal strain vector $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = [\varepsilon_x \ \varepsilon_y \ \gamma_{xy}]^T$, compatible with the deformation displacements. The stresses collected in vector $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = [\sigma_x \ \sigma_y \ \tau_{xy}]^T$ are related to the strains by the classical linear elastic isotropic relation.

3.1. Corotational formulation

The adopted corotational formulation is based on that proposed by Battini [34] for quadrilateral 4-node elements, then extended in [28] to general polygons.

Two coordinate systems are introduced: the global system (O, X, Y) , and the local/corotational one (C, x, y) , which follows the element during its motion and has its origin at the element centroid C , as shown in Fig. 2. The element deformable behavior is analyzed in the local system, then the nonlinear geometric behavior is accounted for through the transformation matrices relating local and global quantities.

The current location of node i and that referred to the initial undeformed configuration are expressed in the global reference system as $\mathbf{X}_i = [X_i \ Y_i]^T$ and $\mathbf{X}_i^0 = [X_i^0 \ Y_i^0]^T$, respectively, and as $\mathbf{x}_i = [x_i \ y_i]^T$ and $\mathbf{x}_i^0 = [x_i^0 \ y_i^0]^T$, in the local coordinate system. Accordingly, the global displacement at node i is defined as:

$$\mathbf{U}_i = \mathbf{X}_i - \mathbf{X}_i^0 \quad (3)$$

and that of the element centroid C results:

$$\mathbf{U}_C = \mathbf{X}_C - \mathbf{X}_C^0 \quad (4)$$

The global displacements of all nodes of the virtual element are collected in vector \mathbf{U} .

The local position of node i in the corotated reference system, after the deformation process can be evaluated as:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{X}_i - \mathbf{X}_C) \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{R} is the matrix ruling the rigid rotation transformation from the initial global reference system to the local one, and depends on the rotation angle θ . Remarkably, the deformation-free part of the element kinematics results from the composition of the rigid translation, expressed by vector \mathbf{U}_C , and rigid rotation θ . Expressions of \mathbf{R} and θ , the

latter evaluated by minimizing the square of the Euclidean norm of the nodal deformation displacements, are reported in Appendix A.

By making use of Eqs. (3)–(5), the deformation displacement at node i is expressed as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_i = \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_i^0 = \mathbf{R} (\mathbf{U}_i + \mathbf{X}_i^0 - \mathbf{U}_C - \mathbf{X}_C^0) - \mathbf{x}_i^0 \quad (6)$$

Deformation displacements at all nodes of each element are arranged in vector $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}$. The latter is linked to the global displacement vector \mathbf{U} by the following variational relation:

$$\delta \tilde{\mathbf{V}} = \mathbf{B} \delta \mathbf{U} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{B} is the compatibility operator, whose detailed derivation is reported in [28], and is computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{B} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G})\mathbf{E}^T \quad (8)$$

being \mathbf{I} the identity matrix and $\mathbf{A} = \left\{ \mathbf{x}_1^{1T} \mathbf{x}_2^{1T} \dots \mathbf{x}_n^{1T} \right\}^T$ the matrix that collects the vectors $\mathbf{x}_i^{\perp} = [-y_i \ x_i]^T$ orthogonal to \mathbf{x}_i . Moreover, \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{G} result as:

$$\mathbf{E} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}^T & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}^T & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \dots & \dots & \mathbf{R}^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{G} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{x}_i^0 T \mathbf{x}_i} \mathbf{A}^0 \quad (10)$$

with $\mathbf{A}^0 = \left\{ \mathbf{x}_1^{0\perp T} \mathbf{x}_2^{0\perp T} \dots \mathbf{x}_n^{0\perp T} \right\}$, being $\mathbf{x}_i^{0\perp} = [-y_i^0 \ x_i^0]^T$.

By invoking the equivalence of the element virtual work evaluated at the global and local levels, the relation between the nodal forces work-conjugate to the displacement global and local vectors, i.e., \mathbf{Q} and $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}$, is obtained as:

$$\delta \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{B}^T \delta \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} \quad (11)$$

Then, the element tangent stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} is evaluated by differentiation of the nodal forces \mathbf{Q} , as follows:

$$\mathbf{K} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} = \frac{\partial (\mathbf{B}^T \tilde{\mathbf{Q}})}{\partial \mathbf{U}} = \mathbf{B}^T \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}}{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{V}}} \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{V}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}^T}{\partial \mathbf{U}} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} \quad (12)$$

In Eq. (12) the material and geometric parts, \mathbf{K}_m and \mathbf{K}_g , of the element tangent stiffness matrix can be recognized. They are cast as:

$$\mathbf{K}_m = \mathbf{B}^T \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}}{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{V}}} \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{V}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} = \mathbf{B}^T \tilde{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{B} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_g = \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}^T}{\partial \mathbf{U}} \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} = \delta \mathbf{E} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G})^T \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} + \mathbf{E} \delta (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G})^T \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} \quad (14)$$

$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}$ is the material tangent stiffness matrix defined in the following section.

3.2. Divergence-free enhanced formulation

In the framework of the corotational approach, the virtual displacement field \mathbf{v} at the generic point of the element domain Ω_E , is defined according to Eq. (6), as follows:

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{R} (\mathbf{U} + \mathbf{X}^0 - \mathbf{U}_C - \mathbf{X}_C^0) - \mathbf{x}^0 \quad (15)$$

According to the main assumption of the VEM, the displacement field \mathbf{v} is not explicitly interpolated in the element domain. Conversely, the

displacement field \mathbf{v} on the element boundary $\partial\Omega_E$, denoted as $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$, is represented as a function of the nodal displacements collected in vector $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}$, by means of the following expression:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}} = \mathbf{N}^V \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \quad (16)$$

being \mathbf{N}^V the matrix of the polynomial shape functions with order k .

Since the displacement field is not explicitly given in the element domain Ω_E , it is not possible to derive the strain by the compatibility equation. Consequently, the approximated strain vector ϵ^P is evaluated as the projection of the (unknown) compatible strain on a subspace of polynomial function with a given degree of the power q . Among the available proposals, we evaluate the approximated strain by enforcing the minimal distance between ϵ^P and $\epsilon(\mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v}$ through the introduction of an energy norm [24,27]. This is defined as:

$$\int_{\Omega_E} (\epsilon^P - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v})^T \mathbf{C} (\epsilon^P - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v}) d\Omega_E \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{D} is the classical compatibility operator for 2D problems under small strain and displacement hypotheses and \mathbf{C} is the material constitutive matrix.

Recognizing that the terms $\mathbf{C}\epsilon^P$ and $\mathbf{C}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{v}$ in Eq. (17) are stress quantities from a mechanical point of view, the approximated stress field σ^P , associated to ϵ^P , is introduced and expressed as follows:

$$\sigma^P = \check{\mathbf{N}} \hat{\sigma} \quad (18)$$

being $\hat{\sigma}$ the vector of the stress parameters and $\check{\mathbf{N}}$ the matrix collecting polynomial interpolation functions with degree up to order q . The latter is here selected so that to avoid spurious energy modes, according to [24] and as better clarified later.

Minimization of the energy in Eq. (17) can now be performed with respect to $\hat{\sigma}$ as:

$$\min_{\hat{\sigma}} \int_{\Omega_E} (\mathbf{C}^{-1} \sigma^P - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v})^T \mathbf{C} (\mathbf{C}^{-1} \sigma^P - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v}) d\Omega_E \quad (19)$$

obtaining the following equation:

$$\int_{\Omega_E} (\mathbf{C}^{-1} \check{\mathbf{N}})^T \mathbf{C} (\mathbf{C}^{-1} \check{\mathbf{N}} \hat{\sigma} - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v}) d\Omega_E = \int_{\Omega_E} \check{\mathbf{N}}^T \mathbf{C}^{-1} \check{\mathbf{N}} \hat{\sigma} d\Omega_E - \int_{\Omega_E} \check{\mathbf{N}}^T \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v} d\Omega_E = 0 \quad (20)$$

Integrating by parts the last term of Eq. (20) and introducing the following definitions:

$$\mathcal{G} = \int_{\Omega_E} \check{\mathbf{N}}^T \mathbf{C}^{-1} \check{\mathbf{N}} d\Omega_E \quad (21)$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{B}} = \int_{\partial\Omega_E} (\mathbf{N}_E \check{\mathbf{N}})^T \mathbf{N}^V d\Gamma_E$$

with \mathbf{N}_E the 2×3 matrix containing the direction cosines of the outward unit normal vectors defined on $\partial\Omega_E$, Eq. (20) leads to the following expression for the stress parameters:

$$\hat{\sigma} = \mathcal{G}^{-1} \tilde{\mathcal{B}} \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \quad (22)$$

To be noted is that Eq. (22) has been derived implicitly assuming a self-equilibrated representation of σ^P , so that the relationship $\mathbf{D}^T \check{\mathbf{N}} = \mathbf{0}$ is assumed to be satisfied.

After the evaluation of the stress parameters by Eq. (22), the projected strain ϵ^P is recovered as:

$$\epsilon^P = \mathbf{C}^{-1} \check{\mathbf{N}} \hat{\sigma} \quad (23)$$

and this can be introduced in the virtual work equivalence or the total potential energy to obtain the solving equation system [24]. The expression of the stiffness matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}$ is derived as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}} = \int_{\Omega_E} \Pi^T \mathbf{C} \Pi d\Omega_E \quad (24)$$

being Π the so-called projector operator, resulting equal to:

$$\Pi = \mathbf{C}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{N}} \mathcal{G}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \quad (25)$$

Note that the material tangent stiffness matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{K}}$ in Eq. (13) corresponds to that defined in Eq. (24) as a result of the assumed linear elastic constitutive behavior.

The adopted formulation, firstly proposed in [24], is characterized by two main advantages:

1. the stiffness matrix in Eq. (24) does not contain zero-energy modes, so that self-stabilized elements are derived;
2. the stabilization-free feature is obtained without introducing internal degrees of freedom.

The first point is achieved by properly selecting the polynomial degree q , which, unlike the classical VEM, is not linked to the polynomial representation used in \mathbf{N}^V , but it is selected so that the number of modes considered in $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}$ is greater than or equal to the element degrees of freedom (DOFs) purged by the number of rigid motions (i.e., modes in $\tilde{\mathbf{N}} \geq n_{DOF} - 3$ in the presented 2D formulation). In [24,28] practical indications are provided on the minimum value to be adopted for q in relation to the number of nodes of the virtual element used.

The second point is realized by adopting divergence-free polynomial representations for $\tilde{\mathbf{N}}$, which satisfy condition $\mathbf{D}^T \tilde{\mathbf{N}} = \mathbf{0}$, ensuring that the term linked to the internal degrees of freedom in Eq. (20) vanishes. This choice leads to computational savings and, in general, to satisfactory results [24,27,28].

3.3. Evaluation of nodal forces equivalent to body loads

In the virtual element framework, the element nodal forces equivalent to body loads, here supposed to be collected in vector \mathbf{F}^b , are computed by exploiting the virtual work of the external loads. Referring to the classical VEM, the load vector is uniformly distributed on each DOF of the element when $k = 1$, i.e., when no internal DOFs are present. Instead, in the case of $k \geq 2$, the only non-zero components of \mathbf{F}^b are those related to the internal DOFs [25].

The virtual element procedure adopted in this work is based on the divergence-free formulation described in the previous section, which leads to self-stabilized elements with no internal DOFs. However, it can be proved that uniformly dividing the total body force at the element nodes produces an unrealistic representation of the element self-weight distribution, although increasing the number of virtual elements discretizing the continuum problem ensures convergence to the exact solution. To avoid this issue, an alternative novel procedure is proposed, capable of properly identifying the components of vector \mathbf{F}^b . This plays a relevant role in the analysis of masonry structures, as self-weight, a typical body load, can significantly affect the structural responses.

Let us consider a generic virtual element E having area Ω_E , thickness w_E , and n nodes; let b_X and b_Y be the forces per unit volume acting along the global X and Y axes, respectively. The total resulting forces, $F_{X,E}$ and $F_{Y,E}$, are computed as:

$$F_{j,E} = w_E \int_{\Omega_E} b_j d\Omega_E \quad j = X, Y \quad (26)$$

where w_E has been assumed to be constant over the element domain.

The total forces in Eq. (26) are usually considered to be applied to the element centroid as in Fig. 3(a), but considering that no internal node is placed at the element centroid, these forces must be assigned to

the DOFs at the element boundary. Hence, vector \mathbf{F}^b takes the following form:

$$\mathbf{F}^b = [F_{X,1} F_{Y,1} F_{X,2} F_{Y,2} \dots F_{X,n} F_{Y,n}]^T \quad (27)$$

Terms $F_{j,i}$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$, $j = X, Y$) in Eq. (27) are evaluated by triangulating the element domain, starting from the centroid, as illustrated in Fig. 3(b) for the example case of $n = 6$ and with reference to the b_Y -component. Denoting with $\Omega_{E,i}$ ($i = 1, \dots, n$) the areas of the resulting triangles, numbered according to local element connectivity, it results:

$$F_{j,i} = \begin{cases} \frac{\Omega_{E,n} + \Omega_{E,1}}{2\Omega_E} F_{j,E} & \text{for } i = 1 \text{ and } j = X, Y \\ \frac{\Omega_{E,i-1} + \Omega_{E,i}}{2\Omega_E} F_{j,E} & \text{for } i = 2, \dots, n \text{ and } j = X, Y \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

The resulting forces (see Fig. 3(c)) represent a load system statically equivalent to the resulting body forces applied at the center of mass, thus well representing the load distribution within the element.

An example of the evaluation of nodal forces equivalent to body load is provided in Appendix B with reference to a virtual element with a general polygonal shape.

4. Interface elements

This section presents the interface formulation. First, the constitutive law, previously adopted in [17,30,33,35], is described. Then, the formulation, until now relying on the small displacement assumption, is extended to the large displacement framework. Finally, computational details are provided.

4.1. Interface constitutive law

The constitutive relation between tractions and displacement jumps at the interface is defined by adopting the cohesive zone model described in [17]. This model is particularly suitable for representing the masonry nonlinear response due to damage, friction, and unilateral contact phenomena occurring at the connection surfaces between blocks [33,35].

In the spirit of the multiscale approach, a representative element of area (REA) is supposed to be linked, at the lower scale, to the typical point of the interface. The REA can experience three different states: undamaged, partially damaged, and completely damaged. Hence, the REA of area A can be split into an undamaged portion, A^u , and a damaged one, A^d . Accordingly, the scalar damage parameter is defined as the ratio between the damaged and the whole area, i.e., $D = A^d/A$.

Assuming as local reference axes of the constitutive model the tangential and normal directions to the interface middle line (x_T, x_N), and denoting with \mathbf{t}^u and \mathbf{t}^d the tractions in the undamaged and damaged regions, respectively, the average tractions \mathbf{t} in the REA result as:

$$\mathbf{t} = \frac{A^u}{A} \mathbf{t}^u + \frac{A^d}{A} \mathbf{t}^d = (1 - D) \mathbf{t}^u + D \mathbf{t}^d \quad (29)$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{t}^u &= \mathbf{C}^S \mathbf{s} \\ \mathbf{t}^d &= \mathbf{C}^S (\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{c} - \mathbf{p}) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

The diagonal matrix $\mathbf{C}^S = \text{diag}\{C_T^0, C_N^0\}$ contains the interface elastic stiffness parameters in the undeformed configuration [22], whereas vectors $\mathbf{c} = [0 \langle s_N \rangle_+]^T$, with $\langle s_N \rangle_+$ denoting the positive part of s_N , and $\mathbf{p} = [p_T \ 0]^T$ account for the nonlinear mechanisms due to unilateral contact and friction, respectively.

As mentioned, and later further detailed, the adoption of a middle surface of the cohesive element in the current configuration to define a proper locus for the evaluation of the normal and tangential directions to the interface is crucial in the development of the large displacement interface formulation. This approach was proposed in the pioneering work in [18] and, since then, this has been widely adopted [21,22].

Fig. 3. Evaluation of nodal forces equivalent to body loads: (a) resulting body force along Y-direction applied to the center of mass, (b) triangulation of the element domain, (c) nodal forces equivalent to b_Y -body load.

It also remarked that cohesive zone modeling at finite displacements requires special conditions (co-axiality between displacement jump and traction vectors) to be satisfied to ensure the balance of angular momentum [22,36]. Since normal and tangential interface responses could be quite different, conservation of angular momentum is here pursued by the hypothesis of small separation displacement before full decohesion and, additionally, by decreasing tractions as the displacement jumps increase during the decohesion process [22,36].

Introducing Eqs. (30) into Eq. (29), the traction-displacement jump constitutive law can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{C}^s(\mathbf{s} - \boldsymbol{\pi}) \quad (31)$$

being $\boldsymbol{\pi} = D(\mathbf{c} + \mathbf{p})$ the inelastic vector including all the nonlinear effects.

The damage variable D evolves satisfying the irreversibility thermodynamic condition of the degrading process, i.e., $\dot{D} \geq 0$, and varies in the range $[0, 1]$. Particularly, the damage parameter attains the maximum value achieved during the loading history, \mathcal{H} , according to the following evolution law:

$$D = 1 - \left\langle 1 - \max\{0, \tilde{D}\} \right\rangle_+ \quad \text{with } \tilde{D} = \frac{\rho - 1}{\rho(1 - \eta)} \quad (32)$$

In Eq. (32), ρ and η are two quantities computed based on the relative displacements using the following expressions:

$$\rho = \sqrt{\left(\frac{s_T}{s_{T,0}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle s_N \rangle_+}{s_{N,0}}\right)^2} \quad (33)$$

$$\eta = \frac{1}{\bar{s}^2} (s_T^2 \eta_T + \langle s_N \rangle_+^2 \eta_N) \quad (34)$$

where $\bar{s} = \|\bar{\mathbf{s}}\|$, with $\bar{\mathbf{s}} = [s_T \langle s_N \rangle_+]^T$. Note that η measures the degree of fracture mode I and II mixity. Indeed, η_T and η_N are the ratios between the elastic threshold ($s_{i,0}$, with $i = T, N$) and the final relative displacements corresponding to full damage for pure shear and tensile fracture mode. These can be expressed as a function of the fracture energies \mathcal{G}_T and \mathcal{G}_N as:

$$\eta_T = \frac{s_{T,0} t_{T,0}}{2\mathcal{G}_T} \quad \eta_N = \frac{s_{N,0} t_{N,0}}{2\mathcal{G}_N} \quad (35)$$

The peak tractions $t_{i,0}$ are associated to $s_{i,0}$ by means of the elastic relationships $t_{i,0} = C_i^0 s_{i,0}$ ($i = T, N$).

The frictional effect can arise in the damaged portion of the REA. Therefore, the evolution of the inelastic slip displacement jump obeys the Coulomb yield function f_Y :

$$f_Y = \mu(\zeta) \langle t_N^d \rangle_- + |t_T^d| \quad (36)$$

where $\mu(\zeta)$ is the friction coefficient which evolves between its initial, μ_i , value and final, μ_f , value, according to the following exponential law:

$$\mu(\zeta) = (\mu_f - \mu_i)(1 - e^{-\xi\zeta}) + \mu_i \quad (37)$$

being ξ the exponential rate parameter and ζ the total friction slip [33, 37].

The only non-zero component of vector \mathbf{p} , i.e. p_T , evolves complying with the classical Kuhn–Tucker loading–unloading conditions and the following flow rule:

$$\dot{p}_T = \dot{\lambda} \text{sign } t_T^d \quad (38)$$

being λ the plastic multiplier.

To summarize, the adopted constitutive law accounts for nonlinear mechanisms caused by tensile and shear microcracks, the re-closure of the tensile cracks in compression, and the frictional phenomena. Bilinear displacement jump–traction curves with softening are obtained for pure tensile and shear states, as indicated by the responses represented with solid lines in Fig. 4(a) and (b), respectively. The effectiveness in capturing the friction phenomenon is clearly shown in Fig. 4(b), where different $s_T - t_T$ curves are reported for qualitative considerations. These have been obtained by assigning a monotonically increasing tangential relative displacement, while keeping constant the assigned normal relative displacement. It can be noticed that greater the normal compressive displacement jump, the higher is the value of the tangential strength of the interface.

Regarding the compression behavior, a linear elastic response is assumed. As a result, the proposed interface formulation, when combined with elastic VEs, is not capable of capturing the complex damage mechanisms that develop under full compression load, such as those occurring in masonry prisms under uniaxial compression. In this case, advanced interphase models could be applied [38].

4.2. Large displacement finite element formulation

A 2 + 2 node interface element, in its reference and current configurations, is depicted in Fig. 5(a).

With reference to the global reference system (O, X, Y), the global displacement of node i , $\mathbf{U}_i = [U_i \ V_i]^T$, is classically defined as the difference between the position vectors $\mathbf{X}_i = [X_i \ Y_i]^T$ and $\mathbf{X}_i^0 = [X_i^0 \ Y_i^0]^T$ (see Eq. (3) and Fig. 5).

Displacements of all nodes of the interface finite element (FE) are collected in vectors \mathbf{U}^s as follows:

$$\mathbf{U}^s = [\mathbf{U}_1^T \ \mathbf{U}_2^T \ \mathbf{U}_3^T \ \mathbf{U}_4^T]^T \quad (39)$$

Similarly, vectors $\mathbf{X}^{0s} = [\mathbf{X}_1^{0T} \ \mathbf{X}_2^{0T} \ \mathbf{X}_3^{0T} \ \mathbf{X}_4^{0T}]^T$ and $\mathbf{X}^s = [\mathbf{X}_1^T \ \mathbf{X}_2^T \ \mathbf{X}_3^T \ \mathbf{X}_4^T]^T$ contain the Cartesian coordinates of the element nodes referred to the initial and current configurations, respectively.

Based on isoparametric mapping, the coordinates of points belonging to the interface middle line in the current configuration, \mathbf{X}_m , and their displacement vector, \mathbf{U}_m , can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{X}_m = \mathbf{N} \mathbf{M} \mathbf{X}^s \quad (40)$$

$$\mathbf{U}_m = \mathbf{N} \mathbf{M} \mathbf{U}^s \quad (41)$$

being \mathbf{M} the averaging operator, whose detailed expression is reported in Appendix C, that provides the coordinates of the initial and final points

Fig. 4. Interface response along the (a) normal and (b) tangential directions.

Fig. 5. Interface finite element: (a) reference and current configurations, (b) division into subdomains.

of the interface middle line, given the positions of the four nodes of the interface FE.

Matrix \mathbf{N} in Eqs. (40) and (41) contains the shape functions and depends on the natural nondimensional coordinate of the element, ξ . Nodes geometrically coincident in the reference configuration have the same shape function, i.e., $N_1 = N_4 = \frac{1-\xi}{2}$ and $N_2 = N_3 = \frac{1+\xi}{2}$.

The displacement jump vector is still denoted as $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ in the finite element formulation, for notational simplicity. This results from the difference between the displacements of the upper and lower faces of the interface:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{N} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} \quad (42)$$

with the kinematic operator \mathbf{L} detailed in Appendix C.

The interface constitutive relation is defined in terms of tangential and normal components to the element average line Γ_m^e referred to the current configuration, as detailed in Section 4.1. Hence, the displacement gap vector in this local frame, $\mathbf{s} = [s_T \ s_N]^T$, has to be computed by pre-multiplying $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ by the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}$ that relates the global (X, Y) and local (x_T, x_N) reference system (see Fig. 5), i.e.:

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}(\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}) \hat{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}(\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}) \mathbf{N} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}) \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} \quad (43)$$

having defined $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{N} \mathbf{L}$. To be noted is that, according to the large displacements setting, matrix $\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}$ depends on the nodal displacements collected in $\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}$, as clearly shown in Appendix C.

Replacing \mathbf{u} with $\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}$, the virtual variation of the internal work in Eq. (2) referred to the interface FE becomes:

$$\delta \mathcal{L}^{\mathfrak{S}} = \delta \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}T} \int_{\Gamma_0^e} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \right)^T \mathbf{t} \, d\Gamma \quad (44)$$

being Γ_0^e the element domain in the reference configuration and $\mathbf{t} = [t_T \ t_N]^T$ the first Piola–Kirchhoff traction vector.

Making explicit the term of the integral in Eq. (44), that is:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} = \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}} \mathbf{Z} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} \quad (45)$$

Eq. (44) can be expressed as follows:

$$\delta \mathcal{L}^{\mathfrak{S}} = \delta \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}T} \int_{\Gamma_0^e} \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}} \mathbf{Z} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} \right)^T \mathbf{t} \, d\Gamma}_{\mathbf{Q}^{\mathfrak{S}}} = \delta \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}T} \mathbf{Q}^{\mathfrak{S}} \quad (46)$$

The integral in Eq. (46) represents the internal force vector $\mathbf{Q}^{\mathfrak{S}}$, accounting for the material, $\mathbf{Q}_m^{\mathfrak{S}}$, and the geometric, $\mathbf{Q}_g^{\mathfrak{S}}$, contributions as follows:

$$\mathbf{Q}^{\mathfrak{S}} = \underbrace{\int_{\Gamma_0^e} (\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}} \mathbf{Z})^T \mathbf{t} \, d\Gamma}_{\mathbf{Q}_m^{\mathfrak{S}}} + \underbrace{\int_{\Gamma_0^e} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} \right)^T \mathbf{t} \, d\Gamma}_{\mathbf{Q}_g^{\mathfrak{S}}} = \mathbf{Q}_m^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{Q}_g^{\mathfrak{S}} \quad (47)$$

According to standard arguments of nonlinear FE formulations, the element stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}^{\mathfrak{S}}$ is obtained as:

$$\mathbf{K}^{\mathfrak{S}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} = \mathbf{K}_m^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g1}^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g2}^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g3}^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g4}^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g5}^{\mathfrak{S}} \quad (48)$$

being $\mathbf{K}_m^{\mathfrak{S}}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{gi}^{\mathfrak{S}}$ ($i = 1, \dots, 5$) the material and geometric contributions to the tangent stiffness matrix, respectively. These terms have the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K}_m^{\mathfrak{S}} &= \int_{\Gamma_0^e} \mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}T} \mathbf{C}_t^{\mathfrak{S}} \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}} \mathbf{Z} \, d\Gamma \\ \mathbf{K}_{g1}^{\mathfrak{S}} &= \int_{\Gamma_0^e} \mathbf{Z}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{t} \, d\Gamma \\ \mathbf{K}_{g2}^{\mathfrak{S}} &= \int_{\Gamma_0^e} \mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}T} \mathbf{C}_t^{\mathfrak{S}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} \, d\Gamma \\ \mathbf{K}_{g3}^{\mathfrak{S}} &= \int_{\Gamma_0^e} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}T} \mathbf{Z}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{C}_t^{\mathfrak{S}} \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}} \mathbf{Z} \, d\Gamma \\ \mathbf{K}_{g4}^{\mathfrak{S}} &= \int_{\Gamma_0^e} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}T} \mathbf{Z}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{C}_t^{\mathfrak{S}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} \, d\Gamma \\ \mathbf{K}_{g5}^{\mathfrak{S}} &= \int_{\Gamma_0^e} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}} \right) \right]^T \mathbf{t} \, d\Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

being $\mathbf{C}_t^{\mathfrak{S}}$ the material tangent stiffness matrix.

The complete geometric tangent stiffness, evaluated as $\mathbf{K}_g^{\mathfrak{S}} = \mathbf{K}_{g1}^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g2}^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g3}^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g4}^{\mathfrak{S}} + \mathbf{K}_{g5}^{\mathfrak{S}}$, is symmetric if the matrix $\mathbf{C}_t^{\mathfrak{S}}$ is symmetric.

4.3. Computational procedure

All the integrals required for the interface element formulation are evaluated numerically using the Gauss integration rule. To improve the accuracy of the integration, especially when nonlinear effects occur in the element domain, the interface element can possibly be divided into

m subdomains, and the Gauss quadrature is performed in each subdomain. While the increase of the quadrature points allows a more accurate integration of higher-order polynomials, dividing the interface into subdomains permits to better integrate some response functions showing a discontinuous trend along the interface domain, such as interface tractions when nonlinear effects due to damage, contact, and friction occur. As an example, Fig. 5(b) shows an interface FE split into three subdomains, each equipped with two integration points.

The details of the solution algorithm implemented in the Finite Element Analysis Program FEAP [39] to solve the nonlinear evolution problem for the interface are contained in the boxes referring to Algorithms 1 and 2. In particular, Algorithm 1 lists the main computational steps needed to update the stiffness matrix and internal force vector, while Algorithm 2 details the procedure developed for the evaluation of the traction vector. Reference is made to the generic Newton–Raphson iteration “ k ” of the current time step “ t_{n+1} ”, within the global solving procedure.

In short words, the input data are all the mechanical parameters, contained in vector \mathbf{d} , the initial coordinates of the interface nodes, listed in vector $\mathbf{X}^{0\mathfrak{g}}$, and the actual nodal displacements $\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$. On the basis of these, the current nodal positions $\mathbf{X}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$ are evaluated and used to compute the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$ ruling the passage from the global to the local interface coordinate system. Moreover, the kinematic operator \mathbf{L} is defined. Afterward, two nested loops start: the first is performed on the subdomains, the latter on the Gauss points. Herein, the shape functions \mathbf{N} are evaluated to calculate the displacement jumps s^k . At this stage, the traction forces must be determined by using the predictor-correct procedure detailed in the Algorithm 2. This involves the computation of the damage-associated variable, ρ^k , and the combination parameter, η^k , of modes I and II for updating the damage variable D^k . Then, if the damaging process is active, the unilateral contact problem and the sliding friction problem are solved. For the latter, a predictor-corrector technique is employed. Considering the sliding friction displacement jumps and the total frictional slip as frozen at the previous time step t_n , the trial normal and shear stresses and the friction coefficient are computed and used to calculate the trial yield function $f_Y^{tr,k}$. Then, if $f_Y^{tr,k} > 0$, the correction phase is performed by updating the inelastic vector, $\boldsymbol{\pi}^k$, and,

Algorithm 1 Computational procedure for large displacement interface finite element with damage and friction constitutive law

Input data: $\mathbf{X}^{0\mathfrak{g}}$, $\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$, \mathbf{d}

1. Update the geometry: $\mathbf{X}^{\mathfrak{g},k} = \mathbf{X}^{0\mathfrak{g}} + \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$
2. Compute operator \mathbf{L} (Eq. C.3) and rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$ (Eq. C.4)
3. Evaluate stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$ and internal force vector $\mathbf{Q}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$
 - start loop on the subdomains m
 - start loop on the Gauss points n_g
 - ◊ evaluate shape functions and construct \mathbf{N} (Eq. C.2)
 - ◊ compute $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{N}\mathbf{L}$
 - ◊ determine displacement jumps s^k (Eq. 43)
 - ◊ compute tractions \mathbf{t}^k (Algorithm 2) and material tangent stiffness matrix $\mathbf{C}_t^{\mathfrak{g},k}$
 - ◊ evaluate terms in Eqs. (C.5), (C.7) and (C.9)
 - ◊ compute material, $\mathbf{K}_m^{\mathfrak{g},k}$, and geometric, $\mathbf{K}_g^{\mathfrak{g},k}$, parts of the stiffness matrix (Eq. 49)
 - ◊ compute material, $\mathbf{Q}_m^{\mathfrak{g},k}$, and geometric, $\mathbf{Q}_g^{\mathfrak{g},k}$, parts of the internal force vector (Eq. 47)
 - ◊ update stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$ and internal force vector $\mathbf{Q}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$
 - end loop on the Gauss points n_g
 - end loop on the subdomains m

Output: $\mathbf{K}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$, $\mathbf{Q}^{\mathfrak{g},k}$

consequently, the tractions at the interfaces, \mathbf{t}^k . Finally, coming back to Algorithm 1, the last operations required to compute the stiffness matrix and internal force vector are performed, consisting of the evaluation of their geometric and material contributions.

5. Numerical applications

This section shows the model capabilities in describing the response of single structural elements and more complex structural schemes. Various numerical simulations are performed, each highlighting a peculiar characteristic of the proposed formulation.

The FEAP code [39], where user elements are formulated and implemented according to the description in previous sections, is used to perform numerical analyses.

5.1. Assessment of the structural capacity of trilitic structures

The behavior of trilitic structures is analyzed here, as this structural scheme has been used extensively throughout history due to its simplicity and relevance in large displacement analyses.

Fig. 6(a) schematically shows the geometry and loading conditions of the analyzed triliton, which is composed of three blocks, a lintel and two pillars, these last with base-to-height ratio, d/h , equal to 0.5. The presence of interfaces is assumed at the contact of the structural elements and between the pillars and the ground. Fixed support condition is adopted. A similar structure has been analyzed in [40] with a rigid block approach.

The numerical model developed here is depicted in Fig. 6(b). It discretizes each block with a single enhanced virtual element with the polynomial degree of the strain/stress approximation, q , equal to 2. One interface element is placed at the contact surfaces, adopting 10 Gauss points for each of the two subdomains considered.

Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio of the blocks are set equal to $E = 5000$ MPa and $\nu = 0$, whereas two sets of mechanical parameters are adopted for the interfaces. These are contained in Table 1 and differ in the value assumed for the friction coefficient, $\mu = \mu_i = \mu_f$.

Algorithm 2 Damage-friction solution procedure for interfaces

Input data: s^k , C_T^0 , C_N^0 , $t_{T,0}$, $t_{N,0}$, G_T , G_N , μ_i , μ_f , ξ

1. Compute damage
 - $\langle s_N^k \rangle_+$, s_T^k
 - ρ^k , η^k (Eqs. 33 and 34)
 - D^k (Eq. 32)
2. Evaluate unilateral effect
 - \mathbf{e}^k
3. Solve friction plasticity problem
 - if $D^k > 0$
 - $\mathbf{p}^{tr,k} = \mathbf{p}_n$, $\zeta^{tr,k} = \zeta_n$
 - $\mathbf{t}^{dtr,k}$ (Eq. 30₂)
 - $\mu^{tr,k}$ (Eq. 37)
 - $f_Y^{tr,k}$ (Eq. 36)
 - if $f_Y^{tr,k} > 0$
 - $\Delta \mathbf{p}^k = \Delta \lambda \frac{\partial f_Y^{tr,k}}{\partial \mathbf{t}^{dtr,k}}$
 - else
 - $\Delta \mathbf{p}^k = \mathbf{0}$
 - endif
 - $\mathbf{p}^k = \mathbf{p}_n + \Delta \mathbf{p}^k$
 - $\zeta^k = \zeta_n + |\Delta p_T^k|$
4. Traction evaluation
 - \mathbf{t}^k (Eq. 31)

Output: \mathbf{t}^k

Fig. 6. Analyzed triliton: (a) geometry (dimensions in meters) and loading conditions, (b) numerical model.

Table 1

Mechanical parameters adopted for the interfaces of the triliton in Fig. 6.

	C_N^0 [N/mm ³]	C_T^0 [N/mm ³]	$t_{N,0}$ [N/mm ²]	$t_{T,0}$ [N/mm ²]	G_N [N/mm]	G_T [N/mm]	$\mu = \mu_i = \mu_f$ [-]
1	0.01	0.01	0.0005	0.020	1.25×10^{-4}	0.2	0.7
2	0.01	0.01	0.0005	0.020	1.25×10^{-4}	0.2	0.3

Compression and shear loads are considered, consisting of the application of vertical forces at the centroid of each block ($P_1 = 10$ kN for pillars and $P_2 = 35$ kN for the lintel), kept constant during the analyses. Then, horizontal varying loads are applied as depicted in Fig. 6(a). The procedure detailed in Section 3.3 is employed to compute the nodal forces simulating the loading conditions described.

The plane stress hypothesis is assumed. Fig. 7 contains the resulting load–displacement global curves relating the applied total horizontal force P ($P = 2\lambda P_1 + \lambda P_2$) to the horizontal displacement U_m , evaluated as the average value of the horizontal displacements of all nodes of the lintel. Focus is now placed on four key curves, three of which have been obtained with the described model coupling VEs and interfaces:

1. the blue solid curve is derived by adopting the hypothesis of Large Displacements (LD) for blocks and interfaces and assuming set 1 of mechanical parameters in Table 1;
2. the blue dashed curve is derived by adopting the Small Displacement (SD) hypothesis for blocks and interfaces (i.e., the nonlinear geometric effects are neglected) and assuming set 1 of mechanical parameters in Table 1;
3. the green solid curve corresponds to the hypothesis of LD for blocks and interfaces with set 2 of mechanical parameters in Table 1;
4. the red solid line represents the limit load evaluated using the Kinematic Approach of Limit Analysis [41].

When the friction coefficient μ is set equal to 0.7, that is $\mu > d/h$, an overturning failure mechanism is observed, as proved by Fig. 8 which contains the deformed configurations of the structure at the last step of the analyses, for the case of small and large displacements assumption. The two configurations appear quite similar, but a closer observation reveals interesting differences. Indeed, the displacement fields exhibited by the structure in the SD case are consistent with infinitesimal kinematics, as each point moves in the direction orthogonal to the line joining the point itself and the related center of rotation. This no longer holds in the case of the LD hypothesis, as pointed out by the detail highlighted at the bottom right in Fig. 8.

Furthermore, the curve deduced under small displacements assumption asymptotically tends to the limit load depicted with the red line in Fig. 7, while the curve evaluated for large displacement hypothesis initially approximates this and, then, departs as the displacement increases. Particularly, a softening branch appears as a consequence of the equilibrium enforced in the deformed configuration of the structure, highlighting the effects of large displacements.

Fig. 7. Load–displacement global curves of the triliton in Fig. 6.

Fig. 8. Deformed configuration of the triliton in Fig. 6 with set 1 of parameters in Table 1 ($\mu = 0.7$), assuming SD and LD hypotheses and with reference to points B and C in Fig. 7.

A more complex collapse mechanism and shape of the global response curve emerge when the friction coefficient μ is set equal to 0.3, that is $\mu < d/h$. In fact, in this case, a mixed overturning-sliding mechanism is observed. At the beginning, the sliding mechanism arises, then, after the horizontal plateau of the green load–displacement curve in Fig. 7, the overturning prevails. This is proved by the triliton deformed configurations reported in Fig. 9, concerning two significant phases of the analysis.

To further validate the presented results, the response of the triliton is analyzed by assuming a denser discretization of the pillars and lintel, involving many triangular elements, and a finer interface mesh. Loading

Fig. 9. Deformed configuration of the trilithon in Fig. 6 with set 2 of parameters in Table 1 ($\mu = 0.3$) assuming LD hypothesis and with reference to points (a) D and (b) E in Fig. 7.

Fig. 10. Deformed configuration of the trilithon in Fig. 6, obtained with triangular mesh and assuming LD hypothesis, at points: (a) C ($\mu = 0.7$) and (b) E ($\mu = 0.3$) in Fig. 7.

conditions schematized in Fig. 6 are imposed in the spirit of the finite element approach, i.e., by assigning equivalent loads at each node evaluated on the basis of the shape functions of 3-node triangular FEs. The resulting response curves, referred to the LD case, are shown in Fig. 7 with dashed violet and dashed black lines for set 1 ($\mu = 0.7$) and set 2 ($\mu = 0.3$) of mechanical parameters, respectively. These are derived by monitoring the central point of the lintel. The perfect overlapping between the curves deduced with the triangular mesh and those derived by discretizing each masonry block with only one VE confirms the accuracy of the proposed modeling approach. Finally, for comparison purpose, Fig. 10(a) and (b) show the deformed configurations of the trilithon at the end of the numerical simulations when the triangular mesh is employed.

5.2. Out-of-plane stability of masonry wall

The response of the masonry wall depicted in Fig. 11(a) is analyzed by applying an eccentric vertical force at the top. The wall overall dimensions are: height $h = 1638$ mm, width $w = 900$ mm and thickness $d = 132$ mm. Brick size and mortar joints thickness are equal to $289 \times 132 \times 45$ mm³ and 18 mm, respectively. As for the mechanical properties, Young's and shear moduli of bricks ("*b*") and mortar ("*m*") result: $E_b = 10000$ MPa, $G_b = 3703.7$ MPa, $E_m = 200$ MPa and $G_m = 74.1$ MPa.

The numerical model developed to explore the out-of-plane behavior of the wall is shown in Fig. 11(b). This is composed of enhanced virtual elements, each of them representative of an expanded brick with dimensions including the thickness of mortar joints. The VEs are equipped with multiple nodes at the top and bottom sides to introduce an accurate interface discretization (see Fig. 11(b)).

The interface mechanical properties derive from those of the mortar layers. Particularly, the elastic normal and shear stiffnesses are evaluated as the ratio between Young's and shear moduli of the mortar and its thickness $t_m = 18$ mm, i.e. $C_N^0 = E_m/t_m$ and $C_T^0 = G_m/t_m$. Double stiffnesses are adopted for the interface at the base. Zero tensile strength is assumed and the other mechanical parameters are set according to [10], that is: $t_{T,0} = 1.0$ N/mm², $G_T = 1.215$ N/mm and $\mu_i = \mu_f = 0.5$.

Although the hypothesis of zero tensile strength may seem unrealistic for simulating mortar joints, it is a conservative assumption usually adopted in design-oriented approaches and analysis of masonry structures [42]. Furthermore, this is initially chosen in view of the

Fig. 11. Clay brick masonry wall: (a) geometry, (b) numerical model and loading conditions.

comparison of the numerical results with the available analytical solution based on the same assumption. However, the structural response is also analyzed below assuming a non-zero tensile strength to highlight the role of this parameter in the load capacity of the wall.

Based on the wall dimensions and loading conditions, the numerical simulation is performed assuming the plane strain hypothesis and the cantilever beam scheme with the wall base fully clamped. A varying vertical force, having initial eccentricity $e = 13.2$ mm from the centroid of the wall section, is applied with arc-length control. Masonry self-weight is neglected. The resulting structural response is reported in Fig. 12(a) in terms of the global curve that relates the applied vertical load P to the horizontal displacement of point A, where the load is applied, considered positive if to the left. The curve exhibits a significant softening branch due to the activation of a flexural collapse mechanism:

Fig. 12. Clay brick masonry wall: (a) load–displacement global curves, (b) damage distribution at the interfaces, at points B and C of the analysis.

Fig. 13. Normalized load–displacement response curve of the wall in Fig. 11 loaded out-of-plane.

initially, each cross-section of the wall is compressed, then, as the load and its eccentricity vary, the interfaces near the base open, inducing section partialization until the sections are fully damaged. This is clearly shown in Fig. 12(b) where the distribution of the damage variable D at the interfaces is plotted in the undeformed wall configurations corresponding to the peak load phase and ultimate step of the analysis.

A different representation of the global response is given in Fig. 13. In detail, the abscissa reports the varying normalized load eccentricity δ/d , being $\delta = e + U_A$. The ordinate axis provides a measure of the load intensity, accounting for the height of the wall h , the section moment of inertia J and the homogenized masonry modulus E_h . The latter is set equal to $E_h = 666.67$ MPa, according to [10]. This type of representation is useful to compare the results obtained with the proposed formulation (blue solid line in Fig. 13) with the analytical solution (dotted blue line in Fig. 13) obtained in [43]. The authors in [43] assessed the instability behavior of compressed dry-stone rectangular pillars loaded with an eccentric load, assuming a no-tension material. It can be noticed that optimal agreement is detected from the comparison of the analytical and numerical curves, although small discrepancies emerge, probably due to the different hypotheses assumed in the two formulations. As a matter of fact, the analytical outcomes are derived in the case of columns made of homogeneous material, whereas the numerical findings consider the heterogeneous nature of the masonry material, by separately modeling bricks and mortar layers.

Finally, the wall response is investigated by assuming for the interfaces the following values of the tensile strength and mode I fracture energy: $t_{N,0} = 0.2$ N/mm² and $G_N = 0.18$ N/mm, respectively. The corresponding load–displacement curve, shown in Fig. 12(a) with dashed line, proves that an increase in the tensile strength of the mortar produces an increase in the peak load, improving both the load-bearing capacity and the ductility.

5.3. Compression-shear behavior of a rubble masonry wall

The compression-shear response of the masonry wall shown in Fig. 14 is numerically reproduced. The specimen was experimentally tested in the laboratory of the ENEA Research center in Casaccia in the framework of the research project “RIPARA” [44].

The wall consists of two panels, placed one over the other and separated by a central concrete curb. Each panel is 0.8 m high, 0.8 m wide, and 0.3 m thick. Two other concrete curbs are located at the base of the lower panel and on the top of the upper panel.

The specimen is made of stone masonry, with the stones collected from the ruins of the city of Accumoli, after the Central Italy seismic sequence in 2016. Mortar characteristics aim at reproducing those of historical masonry buildings.

A Sheppard experimental test was performed. After the application of a compressive load equal to 80 kN at the top curb, a quasi-static cyclic horizontal displacement history was applied at the central curb through a hydraulic jack. Design boundary conditions were aimed at reproducing a fixed base constraint, while preventing horizontal translations and rotations on top. The central curb was constrained only in out-of-plane displacements. The wall response was monitored in terms of both the load–displacement curve, relating the force recorded on the central curb and the imposed horizontal displacement, and crack path.

The numerical model of the wall discretizes each masonry stone with a single polygonal virtual element, incorporating the mortar behavior and the interaction between stones within the interface elements. In detail, one interface FE is used for each interface, assuming 10 Gauss points in the integration rule. To be noted is that a simplified assumption is made, consisting of considering the stone geometry of one of the two sides composing the wall, thus neglecting the through-the-thickness texture, consistent with the 2D formulation of the model. The real out-of-plane thickness of each structural element is accounted for in the numerical model.

Although the lower curb is not explicitly modeled, the numerical boundary conditions reflect the experimental ones, which completely restrain the base of the specimen and prevent the horizontal displacements of the top side. However, additional interface elements are introduced at the top of the upper curb to simulate an intermediate condition between bounded and free rotation. In fact, in contrast to the boundary conditions designed, the wall experienced some rotations of the top face during the experimental test.

Material nonlinearity is concentrated at the interfaces between blocks, assuming the mechanical parameters listed in Table 2. Instead, the interface elements located at the top of the upper curb are assumed to be linearly elastic with interface stiffness values equal to $C_N^0 = 0.03$ N/mm³ and $C_T^0 = 0.015$ N/mm³, thus simulating the effect of the experimentally placed vertical trusses. Young’s moduli and Poisson ratios assumed for the masonry stones (“s”) and the concrete curbs (“c”) are: $E_s = 11000$ MPa, $\nu_s = 0.25$, $E_c = 31500$ MPa and $\nu_c = 0.2$. These are selected based on the stone type, including the stiffness of the mortar joints, and the typical values for good quality concrete, respectively.

A two-step simulation is performed. First, the vertical loads, including the self-weight of the materials ($\gamma_s = 19$ kN/m³, $\gamma_c = 25$ kN/m³) and the additional load at the top, are applied. Then, an increasing horizontal displacement is imposed on the central curb with the aim of numerically reproducing the backbone curve of the cyclic experimental response curve.

Fig. 14. Sheppard test: (a) experimental set-up, (b) geometry of the tested specimen (dimensions in meters).

Table 2
Mechanical parameters adopted for the interfaces of the wall shown in Fig. 14.

C_N^0 [N/mm ³]	C_T^0 [N/mm ³]	$t_{N,0}$ [N/mm ²]	$t_{T,0}$ [N/mm ²]	G_N [N/mm]	G_T [N/mm]	μ_i [-]	μ_f [-]	ξ [mm ⁻¹]
50	25	0.075	0.1	1.7×10^{-3}	6×10^{-3}	0.55	0.1	0.015

Fig. 15. Comparison between experimental and numerical load-displacement global curves obtained for the masonry wall depicted in Fig. 14.

Fig. 15 shows the comparison between the numerical (blue line) and experimental (black line) global response curves. Although the numerical curve exhibits a sudden strength decay around 4 mm, an overall good correlation between the results is observed. A very satisfactory agreement is also obtained in terms of collapse mechanism, as evident from Fig. 16, which shows the numerical and experimental crack patterns obtained at the end of the test, highlighting the formation of a diagonal crack on the upper panel and a very high damage state of the bottom panel.

Finally, the numerical results obtained with the proposed modeling strategy are compared with those derived from a refined model.

Fig. 16. Damage state at the end of the analysis for the wall in Fig. 14: (a) experimental result, (b) numerical result derived from polygonal mesh, (c) numerical result derived from refined triangular mesh. (Amplified deformed configurations of the wall are shown).

The latter discretizes each masonry block with several triangular elements and, consequently, refines the interface discretization (see Fig. 16(c)). The corresponding load-displacement global curve is represented in Fig. 15 with the dashed red line and shows an almost perfect correspondence with the blue curve obtained with the described coarse interface-virtual element mesh. The activated failure mechanism, shown in Fig. 16(c), fully agrees with that derived using the coarse polygonal mesh (see Fig. 16(b)). This comparison further proves both the effectiveness and accuracy of the modeling strategy proposed in Section 3.3 to evaluate the nodal forces equivalent to the masonry self-weight.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, a novel model for the micromechanical analysis of composite materials, composed of blocks with various nature and shape, was proposed. The developed formulation, coupling enhanced virtual elements and interfaces in the large displacement framework, is particularly suitable for the investigation of the mechanical response of masonry structures. Indeed, each virtual element represents a single brick/block with a regular or irregular shape, possibly characterized by modified sizes to include the presence of mortar joints. The interaction between units is simulated by employing interface finite elements.

Geometric nonlinearity due to large displacements was considered for both virtual elements and interfaces, while all the nonlinear material effects were assumed to be concentrated at the interface joints. For the latter, a cohesive zone model was adopted that accounts for damage, unilateral contact, and friction, thus allowing to describe the typical inter-block crack paths, commonly causing the collapse of masonry structures.

The model validation was performed through several numerical tests, comparing the numerical results with experimental outcomes and the available analytical solutions.

To summarize, the following conclusions and novelties can be drawn:

- the coupled use of enhanced virtual elements and cohesive interfaces in the framework of the micromechanical analysis of masonry structures was investigated;
- the proposed formulation allows great mesh flexibility at a low computational cost. Coarse virtual element meshes can be adopted for the units, possibly considering denser discretizations of the nonlinear interface regions. In fact, the admissible virtual elements are polygons of any shape, also characterized by hanging nodes, which can effectively represent blocks with regular and irregular shapes;
- the enhanced virtual element formulation based on the divergence-free polynomial approximation of the stress within the element confirms to be an effective strategy to obtain a self-stabilized element without introducing further internal unknowns;
- explicit expression of all the operators involved in the developed large displacement interface formulation was provided, thus encouraging future implementations of finite element code;
- an effective procedure was developed to evaluate the nodal forces equivalent to body loads in the virtual element context when internal degrees of freedom are not available, allowing the self-weight of the masonry to be correctly represented. The methodology is based on the splitting of the resulting element force at the element nodes based on the influence area of each node, leading to a load system statically equivalent to the force imposed at the element centroid;
- the effects of the geometric nonlinearity were pointed out by comparing results of small and large displacement analyses;
- the versatility of VEM in modeling general polygonal elements was exploited to analyze the compression-shear response of experimentally tested masonry panels composed of irregularly shaped stones. The obtained results, in terms of load–displacement global curve and failure mechanism, agree well with the experimental evidence;
- the results obtained using coarse virtual element meshes for units have been shown to represent in detail those derived from denser discretizations involving many triangular elements, thus testifying to the accuracy of the proposed modeling strategy.

Overall, satisfactory results were obtained, and new perspectives are opening up. The small number of degrees of freedom involved in the coarse virtual element meshes encourages extending the formulation to the 3D case with a view to more complex structural problems. Moreover, the proposed model represents a potentially effective tool to include the nonlinear mechanisms evolving in the blocks, as the adopted enhanced virtual element formulation permits obtaining an improved description of the stress and strain fields within each element compared to the classical VEM. Finally, the model capabilities in describing the main

features of the cyclic response of masonry structural elements will be investigated.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Cristina Gatta: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Marco Nale:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Daniela Addessi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Elena Benvenuti:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Elio Sacco:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A

- Matrices \mathbf{R} is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

being

$$\tan \theta = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^0 (Y_i - Y_C) - y_i^0 (X_i - X_C)}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^0 T (\mathbf{X}_i - \mathbf{X}_C)} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Appendix B

Let us consider the virtual element schematically depicted in Fig. 3 subjected to a body load represented by the element self-weight acting along the negative global Y -axis. Let $\gamma = 25 [F/L^3]$ be the weight per unit volume of the material. The total weight of the element is $F_{Y,E} = \gamma \Omega_E w_E = -3112.5 [F]$, being $w_E = 1 [L]$ the element thickness and Ω_E the area of the element evaluated based on the Cartesian coordinates, X_i and Y_i (with $i = 1, \dots, 6$), of each node contained in Table B.1. Centroid of the element is located at $X_C = 6.4056 [L]$ and $Y_C = 4.2811 [L]$. Note that no specific unit of measurement is adopted for this example case, but lengths are denoted by $[L]$ and forces by $[F]$.

To test the reliability of the procedure developed in Section 3.3, Table B.1 is organized as follows:

- fourth row reports the nodal loads, $F_{Y,i}$, evaluated as in Section 3.3, assuming negative sign to indicate forces directed along the negative Y -axis;
- fifth row lists the lever arms, $b_{h,i}$, of each force with respect to the element centroid;
- sixth row contains the moments of the forces $F_{Y,i}$ evaluated with respect to the centroid assuming counterclockwise moments to be positive.

The sum of all moments M_i in Table B.1 equals zero, thus proving that the nodal forces $F_{Y,i}$ represent a load system statically equivalent to that composed by the total element weight applied at the center of mass.

Table B.1
Example of evaluation of nodal forces equivalent to body load for a virtual element as depicted in Fig. 3.

Node	1	2	3	4	5	6
X_i [L]	0	10	15	16	0	-2
Y_i [L]	0	0	3	7	9	4
$F_{Y,j}$ [F]	-481.225	-468.750	-424.046	-614.684	-650.979	-472.816
$b_{h,i}$ [L]	6.4056	3.5944	8.5944	9.5944	6.4056	8.4056
M_i [FL]	-3082.5	1684.9	3644.4	5897.5	-4169.9	-3974.3

Appendix C

• Matrices **N** and **M** in Eq. (40) result as:

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (C.1)$$

$$\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{N}_1 \mathbf{I} \quad \mathbf{N}_2 \mathbf{I}] \quad (C.2)$$

where **0** and **I** are the 2×2 zero and identity matrices, respectively.

• Matrix **L** is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} -\mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{I} & \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (C.3)$$

• Matrix $\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}$ is defined as:

$$\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}} = \begin{bmatrix} t_X & t_Y \\ n_X & n_Y \end{bmatrix} \quad (C.4)$$

with:

$$t_X = n_Y = \frac{X_2^0 + U_2 + X_3^0 + U_3 - X_1^0 - U_1 - X_4^0 - U_4}{2L_n}$$

$$t_Y = -n_X = \frac{Y_2^0 + V_2 + Y_3^0 + V_3 - Y_1^0 - V_1 - Y_4^0 - V_4}{2L_n}$$

being L_n the length of the interface middle line Γ_m^c in the current configuration.

• The term $\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{ZU}^{\mathfrak{S}}$ results equal to:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{ZU}^{\mathfrak{S}} = [-\mathbf{W} \quad \mathbf{W} \quad \mathbf{W} \quad -\mathbf{W}] \quad (C.5)$$

being:

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ b & -a \end{bmatrix} \quad (C.6)$$

with

$$a = \frac{N_1(U_4 - U_1) + N_2(U_3 - U_1)}{2L_n} \quad b = \frac{N_1(V_4 - V_1) + N_2(V_3 - V_1)}{2L_n}$$

Note that to obtain Eq. (C.5), no derivative with respect to the nodal displacements of the denominators of terms in matrix $\mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}$, i.e. L_n , has been performed, assuming that the length variation of the interface middle line is negligible during the generic load increment.

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{ZU}^{\mathfrak{S}} \right) \right]^T \mathbf{t} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_U \\ -\mathbf{W}_U \\ -\mathbf{W}_U \\ \mathbf{W}_U \end{bmatrix} \quad (C.7)$$

being:

$$\mathbf{W}_U = \frac{1}{2L_n} \begin{bmatrix} a_{1T} & a_{1N} & a_{2T} & a_{2N} & -a_{2T} & -a_{2N} & -a_{1T} & -a_{1N} \\ -a_{1N} & a_{1T} & -a_{2N} & a_{2T} & a_{2N} & -a_{2T} & a_{1N} & -a_{1T} \end{bmatrix} \quad (C.8)$$

with $a_{iT} = N_i t_T$ and $a_{iN} = N_i t_N$ ($i = 1, 2$).

$$\mathbf{Z}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\mathfrak{S}}}{\partial \mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{S}}} \mathbf{t} = [\mathbf{W}_U^T \quad -\mathbf{W}_U^T \quad -\mathbf{W}_U^T \quad \mathbf{W}_U^T] \quad (C.9)$$

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